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Challenges and Prospects of e-learning in the Graduate School Programs of Saint Mary's University

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1. ABSTRACT

This study determined the challenges and prospects of e-learning in the graduate school programs of Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. This study used a concurrent nested mixed-method design involving faculty and students who willingly participated and have experienced an online classes at the university. Data were obtained using a Likert Scale Questionnaire on challenges in e-learning adopted from Ja'ashan (2020) and a summary of the prospects of e-learning in the education of Blezu and Popa (2008). An open-ended questions on challenges and prospects in e-learning were also included in the questionnaire. Graduate students and faculty have the same ratings in their academic, technological, and administrative challenges. The graduate students' perception of e-learning's dynamism, real-time, speed of delivery, consistency, and global reach were significantly higher than the faculty of graduate studies except for collaboration, and convenience. Results of this study were used for crafting an action plan to ensure continual improvement in the delivery of quality education using e-learning in the Graduate Studies.

Keywords: Academic, administrative, blended, flexible, online, and technology

2. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic caused unprecedented damage worldwide (Hermanto et al., 2021). One of the major areas affected by COVID-19 is education (Mushtaha et al., 2022). The transition from traditional to online classrooms had a significant impact, particularly on the engagement between teachers and students, which resulted in a paradigm shift in the teaching-learning process. Hence, online programs replaced traditional classrooms (Khan et al., 2021). The term "e-learning" refers to both online learning and the online delivery of educational materials and related support services to students in the Philippines (Bandalaria, 2009). E-learning offers many opportunities to advance education in academic institutions. It affects positively the educational processes, as opposed to the traditional classroom chalkboard (Oyediran et al., 2020). The most popular learning methodology used in higher education today, particularly during the COVID-19 epidemic, is e-learning (Almaiah, 2020, Butola, 2021). E-learning, termed internet technologies, has expanded the scope of education by advancing classroom learning using virtual learning and teaching communities that communicate online. It is more than just a distance education where resources are simply made available online. E-learning is a virtual learning environment, a campus that is rich in educational and social opportunities for engagement and has the potential to improve flexibility, quality, and focus on education (Blezu and Popa, 2008).

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Several studies were conducted during the two years of the pandemic, e-learning was found to be flexible in place and time. It has numerous positive impacts on the educational processes (Mushtaha et al., 2021; Oyediran et al., 2020). Gupta and Pathania (2021) determined the impact of the google classroom platform on the specific effects of the e-learning platform such as Google Classroom. A similar study was conducted by Gupta and Pathania (2021) in India. Al-Marroof and Al-Emran (2018) investigated the variables influencing Omani students' acceptance of Google Classroom. Studies were also conducted on the effects of online learning on students' mental health, emotional stability, level of stress and anxiety, academic success, and satisfaction with online learning (Lai et al., 2021). Generally, the results of the mentioned studies on google classroom were found to be effective and easy to use. While e-learning was effective and accessible to students, they also had experienced difficulties associated with their mental health and socialization. Hence, hybrid-flexible learning was recommended (Mushtaha et al., 2021).

With the decrease of Covid-19 cases in the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order Number 1, series of 2022 (CHED Memo. No. 1, 2022) states that all state universities and colleges, local universities and colleges, and private Higher Education Institutions (HEI's) may conduct limited face-to-face classes for all program under alert level 1 (Commission on Higher Education, 2022a). Currently, according to David, an OCTA Research Fellow, the nation's average daily attack rate (ADAR) is 2.69 percent per 100,000 people, which is regarded as low. Additionally, the reproduction number dropped from 0.96 on August 17 to 0.91 on August 24 (Sarao, 2022). Hence, with the updated CHED Memorandum Order No. 9, s. 2022, HEIs are guided for the self-reopening of campuses for the conduct of face-to-face classes based on the capability to comply with the minimum public health standard.

As per general guidelines in the memorandum, *“flexible learning in this context is defined as face-to-face learning, online learning, offline learning, or any combination of these modalities. It is the discretion of the HEIs to choose which learning modalities should they operationalize, as long as there will be continuity of learning under any flexible learning modality subject to the condition that the HEIs may require.”* (Commission on Higher Education, 2022b). Pressed with the concern of the modality stated in the memorandum, the graduate studies at Saint Mary's University and Nueva Vizcaya State University use a blended learning modality used. Classes are conducted using synchronous and asynchronous online classes and face-to-face. In the CMO 15, s 2019, it was stated under other requirements particularly on page 25 item 8 on delivery mode, that *the extension graduate program is primarily delivered through face-to-face or classroom-based instruction but can be supplemented with distance learning. If the extension graduate program shall be delivered through blended learning (a combination of face-to-face mode and distance education), other requirements specified in CMO governing open and distance learning shall be complied with by the HEI* (Commission on Higher Education, 2019). The CMO 15, s 2019 is expected to be implemented by 2023. In case the institutions decide to retain the modality used, this study will help graduate students and teachers improve e-learning in graduate programs. Besides, this pandemic taught us that humans are infallible and communities need to be prepared (Khanna, 2020). Political, scientific, and societal agenda put premium on pandemic preparedness and planning which were influenced by the accomplishments and shortcomings of the global response to COVID-19 (IEEE Pulse, 2022). Such conditions demanded contingency plans to prepare not only in improving e-learning but

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in preparing for post and for future pandemic scenarios. Additionally, this study was deemed beneficial to the graduate program administrators in order to start implementing the proposed action plan, which is the final output of this study. This will also be beneficial to both graduate faculty and students who will be more empowered in using e-learning in the teaching and learning process.

Hence, this study determined the challenges and prospects of e-learning among graduate students and faculty-selected university in Nueva Vizcaya. This study was the basis for proposing an action plan that will ensure continual improvement in the delivery of quality education using e-learning in the graduate programs of Saint Mary's University. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. determine the challenges in e-learning among graduate students and faculty;
2. determine the prospects of e-learning among graduate students and faculty;
3. compare the mean rating of the participants in the challenges and prospects in e-learning when grouped by type of participants; and
4. propose an action plan in improving the e-learning of the graduate students.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study used a concurrent nested mixed-method design. In this design, qualitative and quantitative data were gathered at the same time, but one type of data were given greater weight than the other (Creswell et al., 2003). The study was particularly conducted at the School of Graduate Studies, Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The school envisioned as a caring and dynamic center of professional service and development committed to nurturing professionals exemplifying excellence, innovation, and passion for Christ's mission. The school dedicates itself to vigorously guiding professionals in the utmost development of their potential for local and global relevance and responsiveness; passionately empowering professionals with values, attitudes, and insights for effective and productive practice of their profession, and for becoming community-supportive individuals; and continuously challenge professionals to explore and pursue relevant, innovative and breakthrough ideas through research and development. For School Year 2022-2023, the school resorted to blended learning modality, both face-to-face and online learning.

Table 1 shows the number of graduate programs in the target universities.

Table 1

Number of Graduate Programs offered at Saint Mary's University

University	Masteral	Doctoral
SMU	13	4

The participants of the study were both faculty and students in the Graduate School Programs. All enrolled Graduate students at Saint Mary's University in the first semester, SY 2022-2023 are the participants of the study. There are 411 graduate students currently enrolled at SMU. The target of the study was a total enumeration. However, this was trimmed down based on the criteria and the willingness to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

Officially enrolled graduate students who experienced online classes.

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Exclusion criteria: Graduate students who did not experience attending online classes were not included in the study. Graduate students who rarely (1 to 3 times only since the start of the classes) attend his/her online classes were withdrawn from the study.

All willing faculty with teaching load during this semester, SY 2022-2023, and conducting online classes through Zoom or other online platforms were included in the study.

All the faculty and students were given a questionnaire. However, those who met the criterion and those who willingly participated were considered the participants.

There were six main instruments used in this study. The Likert Scale Questionnaire on challenges in e-learning for faculty was adopted from Ja'ashan (2020). The participants were asked to rate each item of the questionnaire from 1 to 4. Scale 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for disagree, 3 for agree, and 4 for strongly agree. The questionnaire comprises three domains namely: academic challenges, technological challenges, and administrative challenges. The instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.76. Table 2 shows the distribution of the items per domain.

Table 2

Domain, Number of Items, and Item Location

Domain	Number of items	Item Location
Academic challenges	6	Items 1 to 6
Technology challenges	7	Items 7 to 13
Administrative challenges	6	Items 14 to 19

The Likert Scale Questionnaire on challenges in e-learning for students was also adopted from Ja'ashan (2020). The questionnaire determined the challenges encountered by the students. The questionnaire used a scale of 1 to 4. It also comprises three domains like the questionnaire for faculty. Table 3 shows the number of items per domain and their location in the questionnaire. The reliability coefficient index of the instrument was 0.80.

Table 3

Domain, Number of Items, and Item Location

Domain	Number of items	Item Location
Academic challenges	3	Items 1 to 3
Technology challenges	3	Items 4 to 6
Administrative challenges	5	Items 11 to 15

The Likert Scale questionnaire on the prospects in e-learning for faculty and students was developed from the Prospects of e-learning in the education of Blezu and Popa (2008). The items comprise statements about dynamism, real-time, collaboration, speed of delivery, convenience, consistency, and global reach. Similar statements are also in the questionnaire for students; however, the statements are in the first person. The questionnaires for faculty and students were validated by experts and they were pilot tested in the undergraduate programs of Saint Mary's University, particularly for the faculty and students who experienced e-learning during the pandemic. The Cronbach's Alpha was greater than 0.70. The validation tool used was the research instrument validation sheet adapted from the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya.

The open-ended questionnaire on challenges and prospects of e-learning for faculty and students allowed them to recommend or suggest improvements to reduce or address their challenges. It also asked about other challenges encountered not covered in the

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questionnaire. Other questions required the participants to cite their experiences regarding the prospects of e-learning and to share how they envision the use of e-learning in the future. There were four initial questions placed in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by a qualitative analyst.

This study used quantitative and qualitative data analysis in answering the research problems. In determining the challenges and prospects in e-learning the mean and standard deviation were computed. The mean scores were interpreted using Table 4.

Table 4

Guide for Interpretation

Scale	Challenges	Prospects
1.00-1.49	Highly a challenge	Highly not a Prospect
1.50-2.49	A challenge	Not a prospect
2.50-3.49	Not a challenge	a Prospect
3.50-4.00	Highly not a challenge	Highly a Prospect

In comparing the mean rating of the participants in the challenges in e-learning when grouped by type of participant, t-tests for Independent Samples were computed for academic and technological challenges. Mann Whitney U test was used for administrative challenges because assumptions on normality were not met. Mann Whitney U test was also used in comparing the prospects.

Finally, in coming up with an action plan for improving the e-learning of the graduate students, the results from the Likert Scale and open-ended questionnaire, and the suggestions and recommendations of the participants were utilized.

Upon the approval of the evaluators, this study was submitted for approval to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at 2nd floor, rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email:reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). There is no known conflict of interest in this study. All the data were gathered and treated with the utmost confidentiality. Also, the identity of the participants was kept confidential.

To avoid deception, participants were informed about the true purpose and nature of the study. Informed consents were given to them and only those willing to participate were asked to answer the questionnaires. There is no known risk in the participation of the study.

4. RESULTS

Section 1. Challenges in e-learning among graduate students and faculty

Table 5 shows the means and standard deviations of each of the identified indicators of the challenges in e-learning among graduate students.

Table 5

Challenges in e-learning among the graduate students

Academic Challenges Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Lack of interaction between students and teaching staff	2.26	.829	A challenge

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Academic Challenges Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
2. Insufficient time to accomplish online exams/assignments	2.47	.902	A challenge
3. Inaccessibility of course notes/materials	2.08	.688	A challenge
Administrative Challenges			
4. Problems with internet access	2.98	.883	Not a challenge
5. Negative comments about E-learning	2.04	.662	A challenge
6. Inadequate ICT and E-learning infrastructure in school	2.16	.704	A challenge
Technology Challenges			
7. Lack of technology/software required for home access	2.55	.856	Not a challenge
8. Lack of technical support/advice	2.51	.857	Not a challenge
9. Inaccessibility of audio/video material, PDF, PowerPoint	2.06	.785	A challenge
10. Lack of training courses provided by the institution	2.10	.671	A challenge
11. The software of E-learning is too complicated to use	1.82	.684	A challenge
Others			
12. Lack of knowledgeable person at home who can help when technical problems arise	2.55	.966	Not a challenge
13. Physical setting at home is not conducive for e-learning because of noisy surroundings	2.65	.891	Not a challenge

Table 6 displays the challenges in e-learning among the faculty of graduate studies.

Table 6
Challenges in e-learning among the faculty

Academic Challenges Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Insufficient time to develop E-learning content and exams/assignments	2.75	.622	Not a challenge
2. Limited interaction between students and teaching staff	2.67	.492	Not a challenge
3. Lack of awareness regarding ways to integrate the software into teaching	2.25	.622	A challenge
4. Inaccessibility of PowerPoint / PDF/ data projection during lectures	1.75	.622	A challenge
5. Inaccessibility, of course, notes/feedback about materials	1.92	.793	A challenge
Technology Challenges			
6. Inadequacy of technology/software required for home access	2.33	.779	A challenge
7. Lack of technical support/advice	2.25	.754	A challenge
8. Lack of necessary adaptive technology	2.25	.754	A challenge
9. Technological background is inadequate	2.33	.779	A challenge
10. Lack of training courses provided by institutions	2.25	.754	A challenge
11. The software of E-learning is too complicated to use	2.33	.651	A challenge

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Academic Challenges Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Administrative Challenges			
12. Lack of administrative support and encouragement	2.00	.603	A challenge
13. Problems with internet access	2.58	.669	Not a challenge
14. Negative comments about E-learning	2.08	.793	A challenge
15. Inadequate ICT (Information Communication Technology) and E-learning infrastructure	2.50	.674	Not a challenge

Section 2. Prospects in e-learning among graduate students and faculty

Table 7 displays the means and standard deviations of the prospects in e-learning among graduate students.

Table 7

Prospects in e-learning among Graduate Students

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Dynamism: I progress at the pace that suits me best, at the time that suits me best while getting the information that I need.	3.45	.577	A Prospect
Real time: I have access to information that is correct and up to date through the web, information databases or university or company intranets.	3.31	.616	A Prospect
Collaboration: I am able to meet in a virtual space with other students and practitioner experts to discuss issues, answer questions and even participate in simulations and management games without having to leave home.	3.26	.717	A Prospect
Speed of delivery: Learners are able to access the right sort of training at the right time.	3.18	.623	A Prospect
Convenience: I have access to needed materials when I want them.	3.20	.749	A Prospect
Consistency: I have access to the same materials.	3.29	.610	A Prospect
Global reach: I, regardless of where I am, receive the same message and I am able to engage with my classmates and practitioners globally.	3.41	.572	A Prospect

As gleaned in Table 7, e-learning allows dynamism, real-time, collaboration, speed of delivery, convenience, consistency, and global reach for graduate students.

Table 8 displays the prospects in e-learning among faculty of graduate students.

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Table 8
Prospects in e-learning among Faculty

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Dynamism: Learners progress at the pace that suits them best, at the time that suits them best while getting the information that they need.	2.83	.389	A Prospect
Real time: Learners have access to information that is correct and up to date through the web, information databases or university or company intranets	2.83	.389	A Prospect
Collaboration: Learners are able to meet in a virtual space with other members and practitioner experts to discuss issues, answer questions and even participate in simulations and management games without having to leave their office or home	2.92	.289	A Prospect
Speed of delivery: Learners are able to access the right sort of training at the right time	2.75	.452	A Prospect
Convenience: Learners have access to needed materials when they want them	2.92	.289	A Prospect
Consistency: Learners have access to the same materials	2.92	.289	A Prospect
Global reach: Learners regardless of where they are receive the same message and are able to engage other learners and practitioners globally	2.92	.289	A Prospect

Section 3. Comparison of the mean rating/mean rank of the participants in the challenges and prospects in e-learning when grouped by type of participant

Table 9
Difference in Challenges in e-learning

Domains	Type	N	Mean/mn rank ^a	SD	Test Statistics
Academic	faculty	12	2.27	.535	t(61)=-.006, p=.995
	student	51	2.27	.663	
Technology	faculty	12	2.29	.671	t(61)=.413, p=.681
	student	51	2.21	.623	
Administrative	faculty	12	29.33 ^a	-	U=274, p=.571
	student	51	32.63 ^a	-	

Table 10 displays the comparison of the mean rank when grouped by type of participant.

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Table 10
Difference in Prospects in e-learning

Domains	type	N	Mean Rank	Test Statistics
Dynamism	faculty	12	18.33	U=142, p=.001**
	student	51	35.22	
	Total	63		
Real time	faculty	12	21.42	U=179, p=.011**
	student	51	34.49	
	Total	63		
Collaboration	faculty	12	23.75	U= 207, p=.050
	student	51	33.94	
	Total	63		
Speed of delivery	faculty	12	23.00	U=198, p=.029*
	student	51	34.12	
	Total	63		
Convenience	faculty	12	25.21	U=224.5, p=.111
	student	51	33.60	
	Total	63		
Consistency	faculty	12	23.17	U=200, p=.030*
	student	51	34.08	
	Total	63		
Global reach	faculty	12	20.33	U=166, p=.005**
	student	51	34.75	
	Total	63		

*significant at 0.05

**significant at 0.01

Section 4. Action plan in improving the e-learning of the graduate students.

Table 11 displays the themes coded from the open-ended questionnaires and the suggested possible actions to address the concerns.

Table 11
Themes and Suggested Actions

Themes	Possible actions
Academic	
Limit time and reduce requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management seminar for the graduate students (example: Pomodoro technique) • Seminar on well-being and stress management
Trainings and seminars for more dynamic teaching and support	Training and seminars for making lessons more interactive.
Encourage interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of multimedia • Interactive assessments • Use of games/gamification

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Themes	Possible actions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaboration and teamwork • Use of personalization • Feedback and support
Request for blended learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct a survey on blended learning.
Availability of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review materials in the library, and encourage faculty members to use eBooks and electronic resources. • Ask copy from the library and disseminate them to the faculty and graduate students. • Ask the assistance of the program head/to create a committee to evaluate materials placed in the LMS to ensure the quality and relevance to the lesson
weekdays schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refrain/ Avoid weekday classes except if the students are all scholars.
orientation of target output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct regular Online Orientation
More trainings for faculty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of technology/software/ IT facilities in the preparation of materials
Creation of better policies online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review existing guidelines • Allow both faculty and students comment/critique the policies online. • Revise accordingly.
Technology	
Prompt or immediate technical support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forward concern of the students to the CICT regarding immediate technical support.
Availability of sources even offline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage faculty members to create handouts/modules • Inquire assistance of the program heads and professors to evaluate the quality of the materials
more trainings and technology system support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct training in using technology
Provision of webcam, ear/headphones; portable WIFI;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forward to the person concern • Create online help-desk to address learners' concern on LMS
regular updating of the features of the LMS to improve service delivery”,	
“Make available useful apps no longer in the LMS like bigbluebutton”,	
Manpower was also reiterated to provide assistance	
Administrative	
Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientations are conducted every semester and reiterate to the teachers.
Grade transparency	

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Themes	Possible actions
Secure or all in good condition platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No control in case it is due to the service provider.
Administration should ensure continuity in the use of the LMS even with F2F classes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To forward to the person in charge
More investments on infrastructure	
WIFI access school-wide	
Subscriptions to software in preparing lessons	
Others	
Data privacy	
Regular need survey and analysis	

Based on the possible actions identified to address the needs of the respondents. An action plan was created for the possible actions that can be conducted to improve e-learning at Saint Mary's University.

Table 12 displays the draft action plan to improve e-learning at Saint Mary's University.

Table 12

Action Plan to Improve e-Learning

Target Month	Event (Name and Description)	Event Type (service, educational, fundraising, and social activities)
August	<p>Finalization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalize the action plan with the help of the dean, and program heads of the graduate studies. Identify possible speakers for the capacitation training for the faculty Identify speakers for seminars for students such as time management, stress management, and well-being seminar. Online Orientation for 1st-semester classes Creation of Evaluation Committee (LMS materials and resources) 	Service

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Target Month	Event (Name and Description)	Event Type (service, educational, fundraising, and social activities)
September	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seminar on time management, stress management, and well being 	Educational
October	Seminar on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> use of multimedia Interactive assessments Use of games/gamification collaboration and teamwork Use of personalization Feedback and support 	Educational
November	Seminar on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials/module preparations 	Educational
December	Report Writing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narrative report and evaluation of all seminars conducted 	Service

5. DISCUSSIONS

Academic, administrative, and technological challenges were experienced by graduate students in e-learning. Graduate students do not consider internet access, lack of technology/software required, technical support/advice, or lack of knowledgeable person and the physical setting as challenges in e-learning.

The graduate students stressed the need of longer time in complying with their activities and requirements and the possibility of having lesser requirements.

Pedro (not his real name) said, *“Longer periods and leeway in taking examinations and submitting requirements online because students are always on a hurry just to meet immediate deadlines and we are given limited time to elucidate everything we know in an online examination.”*

Similar statement from Maria (not her real name) who said that, “more time in accomplishing assignments.”.

The Graduate school students also suggested to limit the requirements given to them. For instance, Juan (not his real name) said, *“There should be less activities. We should be able to haggle with the teacher since most of us are also working.”*

Graduate students also suggested conducting training and seminars for teachers, encourage interaction and request for blended learning. As suggested by Mark (not his real name) said, *“Make Camera on a mandatory so that there is more interaction between the class and to make sure that the student is present all the time”*

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Also, Riye (not her real name) stated that *"I hope there will be face-to-face classes. or blended classes. Although it would be a disadvantage for students who are abroad. So, online still works for me."*

In terms of technological challenges, Graduate students' concerns were technical support, and the availability of materials even offline. As mentioned by Liam, *"Immediate technological support team that could cater the queries of students regarding technological matters., Perhaps, training to become more adept on technology that are being used on e-learning. If not, provide new technologies that are sufficient, but are not that complicated"*. In terms of administrative challenges, graduate students were requesting assistance to e-learning accessibility particularly in calling hotlines or seeking help from the instructors, orientations, and transparency, especially in grading, and more support from the administrative staff during enrollment. Chadly said, *"Asking for guidance on what next subjects to take. i had a struggle of this almost every sem since it is online class, there might be struggle in communication so I have experienced petitioning subject before, which I totally would like to avoid. Also, struggle with the accounting, no updates provided when asked of our balance/statement of accounts. Overall, admin from graduate studies are very accommodating."* Another concern raised by the graduate students was on data privacy. Trista said, *"Concerns on digital imprints, data privacy and confidentiality -- There are lectures in the virtual classroom that are fully recorded. Sometimes, these lectures are also being used as materials in other virtual classes as is (not edited), including some information of and exchanges among students and lecturers, and are even uploaded online (e.g. YouTube). Sharing fully recorded lectures across classes is efficient, but this might lessen confidence in virtual classroom participation. Students might hesitate to openly share ideas, sometimes raw or controversial ones, during class as they are being recorded and possibly shown to others. This might weaken the feeling of security/safety of students and thus, defeat the free flow of ideas in the virtual classroom."*

Online learning challenges depend on how the modality was adapted to online education (Almahasees et al., 2021). Mushtaha et al. (2022) found both positive and negative results or most significant challenges and opportunities of online learning. In this study, e-learning was also found to be flexible (Mushtaha et al., 2022) but had not seen any effect on mental health and socialization. However, students emphasized that they need more time in doing their requirements or activities in their online courses. Hence, this may also affect their mental health. Moreover, students also pointed out about the interaction between the teachers and the students and even requested for a blended learning approach. This was highlighted by Hermanto et al. (2021) who identified that some of the challenges and effectiveness of online learning depend heavily on several interconnected elements, including students, instructors, and learning the available resources and technologies.

Faculty members of Graduate Studies encountered academic, administrative, and technological challenges in e-learning. However, they considered insufficiency in time and limitation in interaction as challenges. Faculty members do not consider internet access as a problem while there is an inadequacy in ICT and e-learning infrastructure. In terms of academic challenges, faculty suggested trainings that will focus on the use of technology/software/ IT facilities and the preparation of materials. They also pointed out that the readiness of the students in independent learning must also be considered, as better policies that will promote e-learning.

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In terms of technological challenges, faculty members suggested *“Provision of webcam, ear/head phones; portable WIFI; regular updating of the features of the LMS to improve service delivery”, “make available useful apps no longer in the LMS like bigbluebutton”, and “more trainings and technology system support.”* Manpower was also reiterated to provide assistance. In terms of administrative challenges, some suggestions scoped from the faculty members were on:

“(1) Administration should ensure continuity in the use of the LMS even with F2F classes”

“(2) More investments on infrastructure”

“(3) Regular needs analysis and student satisfaction surveys”

“(4) WIFI access school-wide”

“(5) Increase funding to strengthen IT facilities and improve faculty IT and digital edtech skills”

“(6) There are lots of software that can help in the preparation of lessons. The good ones are the ones that must be paid for. There are plenty of laboratory simulations to substantiate lessons, these must be subscribed with.”

As perceived by the faculty of Graduate School Studies, e-learning allows dynamism, real-time, collaboration, speed of delivery, convenience, consistency, and global reach for graduate students. Oyediran et al. (2020) also determined the prospects and limitations of e-learning. However, they reiterated that despite the prospects of e-learning, the limitations of e-learning are significant barriers to e-learning use and future possibilities at Nigeria's private tertiary institutions.

The academic, technology, and administrative challenges encountered by both faculty and students were the same. Paralle results were revealed by Ashraf et al. (2021) that all the students regardless of educational level and sex have the same problems encountered. Whereas, Ja’ashan (2020) identified that challenges in academics, administration, and technology were the primary challenges in e-learning in Saudi Arabia. Students' rating was significantly higher in terms of dynamism, real-time, speed of delivery, consistency, and global reach than the faculty. However, the rating was the same in terms of collaboration and convenience. Ja’ashan (2020) identified that the primary benefit of using e-learning was its usability and flexibility that can enrich students' learning experiences including improvement in communication.

Based on the identified challenges of students and faculty members of graduate studies, some suggestions were to conduct seminar such as time management, well being and stress management to help the students on their concern on complying with their requirements given them an ample time. Training and seminars for making lessons more interactive were also considered such as topics on use of multimedia, interactive assessments, use of games/gamification, collaboration and teamwork, use of personalization and feedback and support.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Both faculty and graduate students experienced academic, administrative and technological challenges. Students better appreciate the e-learning's dynamism, real-time, speed of delivery, consistency, and global reach or what the e-learning is capable of than that of the faculty members. However, both faculty and students perceived the e-learning's capability of collaboration and convenience. The action plan for improving the e-learning of graduate

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studies suggested possible training and development programs that will address the challenges encountered by both faculty and students.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Implementation of the activities in the action plan is recommended to address the academic, technological, and administrative challenges encountered by both faculty and graduate students. The dynamism, real-time, speed of delivery, consistency, global reach, collaboration, and convenience should be strengthened while using the e-learning modality.

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